

ACCELEROMETER-BASED SYNCHRONISATION PROTOCOL FOR MUSIC-ALIGNED MEASUREMENTS OF DISTRIBUTED DATALOGGING WEARABLES

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ABSTRACT

Many commercial wearable biosensors can be set to record (datalogging) cardiac activity, motion, respiration, and other signals in devices easily worn during group musical activities. However, despite offering research-relevant sample rates and exportable data formats, these commercial units are not designed for high accuracy synchronisation to external clocks. Anticipated uses like solo exercise and sleep monitoring do not require inter-device alignment below a few seconds, while musical activities feature discernible events within 200 ms and action alignment between participants under 10 ms. In the absence of a mechanism to digitally communicate timing triggers across datalogging devices, we have developed a synchronisation protocol to embed audio-aligned cues in active accelerometers to allow reassignment of timestamps after recording. This process substantially improves inter-unit signal alignment, correcting initialisation time offsets and clock drift to within accelerometer sample rate in recordings spanning 3 to 10 hours. Implemented in 15 recording sessions over 5 experiments, involving 9 to 95 units of various datalogging wearables, the resultant datasets support analysis of inter-participant coordination across signals and, with audio-based dynamic time warping, relatively high precision comparisons of sensor measurements to repeated musical events, all outside of laboratory conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Technologies for recording physiological signals such as heart rate have proliferated far outside of clinical and laboratory settings. Some of these support data-streaming, transmitting to computer for recording with multiple options for managing synchronisation with current audio and/or video recordings. However, collecting data streams for many devices concurrently requires multiple receiving machines, sometimes with the obligation to transmit sensitive physiological measurements to the cloud, and also with the risk of transmission interference within specific mediums. Logging measurements within devices for later retrieval can be a cheaper, safer, more portable, and more

reliable process, so long as the data-stamping clocks within devices can be brought into alignment.

For physiological signals like cardiac activity, sensor systems vary substantially in their invasiveness and robustness. Out-of-laboratory biosensor measurement systems are convenient for their inherent mobility, sensor design compatible with active condition (sport), and relatively easy deployment. The Equivital Life Monitor¹ vest and the Movesense² ECG belt³ record cardiac activity with sufficient reliability for heart rate monitoring without adhesive electrodes (See these sensor units in Figure 3.) Participants can be fit with active sensors in 2 to 5 minutes, and repeat users can don the same equipment in under a minute with zero waste. This was a big improvement from out-of-lab deployments of the wireless Delsys Trigno sensor system⁴, which required several minutes for experimenters to apply gel electrodes on participants and sometimes lost electrode contact with perspiration.

However, despite these advantages for field recordings of group musical activities, these datalogging wearable biosensors are not constructed for high precision concurrent recording. Many commercial wearables can't receive triggers for clock synchronisation or recording commands, simultaneous or otherwise. Some of these systems claim to become synchronised with initialisation or data retrieval. The Equivital sensor units (SEM) and Axivity AX3 sensors⁵ take the computer clock time when initialised, and Movesense sensors can append to data files the end of recording time according to the clock of the downloading mobile phone. These mechanisms improve the alignment of timestamps between devices, but often only to within a few seconds, with differences increasing over time as individual device clocks drifted. Sensor-alignment correction is necessary to make such logged measurements usable for music coordination research, and embedded parallel cues have been used to correct alignment between accelerometers before [1].

The idea of embedding a sharp synchronisation cue for alignment with audio recordings was initially implemented with participants tapping on their own sensors [2]. At

¹eqLifemonitor device: <https://equivital.com/products/eq02-lifemonitor>

²Movesense Flash device: <https://www.movesense.com/movesense-flash/>

³Movesense ECG Belt: <https://www.movesense.com/cardiorthm/>

⁴Trigno Wireless Biofeedback System: <https://delsys.com/support/documentation/>

⁵Axivity AX3 sensor: <https://axivity.com/userguides/ax3/>

MusicLab Copenhagen, audience participants in the concert experiment venue and online recorded their body motion via the accelerometer sensors on their own mobile phones with the MusicLab app. To anchor measurements to concert events, participants were played a series of beeps at two tempi and instructed to listen (to entrain) and tap along. These coordinated taps allowed their motion measurements to be aligned to within 100 ms. A similar tap-based synchronisation method was used with an orchestra: all members wearing Equivital sensors listened and tapped along to a few beeps before each concert. Professional musicians tapping performance was substantially more in synch, resulting in between-device alignment to within 44 ms (standard deviation). However, this precision is still insufficient for some research questions and human variability and unreliability made the clock correction process exceedingly time consuming. A similar shaking procedure was used for a virtual concert, with less controlled cueing, allowing alignment improvements from minutes to seconds [3]. Concurrent mechanical agitation of sensors has also been used for quality assessment across units in device performance validation [4].

This paper describes a substantial improvement on the tapping protocol for experiments where devices can be set to record accelerometry before they are distribution to participants and after the musical activity. A layer of human variability was removed from two additional multi-day orchestral concert experiments (45 to 95 concurrently recording sensor units) with the help of a shaker table and long-running audio recorder. In smaller experiments, hand-held bundles of 10-25 sensors were gathered for simultaneous, sharp, and audible displacements. The following describes the shaking protocol, the synchronisation cue retrieval process, key materials for the large scale deployments, and the temporal alignment gains under ideal and less than ideal circumstances.

2. SHAKER-AUDIO PROTOCOL

The premise of this synchronisation process is quite simple. Assuming the clocks in active wearable sensor units drift linearly, two well-spaced embedded cues shared across devices should allow all measurements to be aligned to within a sample point. To connect these measurements to experiment events, an audio recorder is set record continuously, from the first synch cues, through the musical activities, until after the second synch cue. More explicitly, for any multidevice datalogger recording session, the researchers must:

1. Initialise and set all sensor devices to record accelerometry.
2. Gather devices into a solid shakable arrangement: in layers on a shaker table for many sensors, in two tight hand-held bundles for smaller numbers.
3. Turn on the audio recorder and verbally report recording conditions (date, experiment, external clock time).

4. Place the audio recorder near the shaker table or location of agitation.
5. Shake or smack together the sensors with an uneven sequence of strong and loud hits over 5 to 15 seconds.
6. Proceed with sensor distribution to participants.
7. Carry the active audio recorder to the group activities of interest to capture the timing of events.
8. Gather sensors from participants after the group activities, all still active and recording accelerometry, and arrange on the shaker table or bundle for agitation.
9. Place the active audio recording again next to the action.
10. Shake or smack together the sensors with a different uneven sequence of strong and loud hits.
11. Turn off audio recorder and sensors, and export all data for offline synchronisation.

Depending on the number and type, the process to manipulating devices to initialise and set recording can take a few minutes. And for long recordings, retrieval of logged data can take minutes to hours. Thus far, the additional steps to add synchronisation cues only adds a few minutes on either end of a recording session, once all sensor units are retrieved.

2.1 Cue extraction

Percussive hits facilitate the extraction of the cue sequence from the audio recordings. Excerpts of the full audio file can be cut around each cue time. A python notebook with sound processing libraries and a simple peak extraction algorithm can extract to timing of hits from peaks in the audio wave's RMS. Figure 1 shows the extracted RMS and detected peak sequence from a recent experiment where a dozen Movesense sensors in a foam case were hit against a hotel doorjam.

Figure 1. Synchronisation cue hit timing extracted from the RMS of the concurrent audio recording during a recent pilot experiment. Peaks selected from local maxima with a percentile threshold.

Besides determining a relevant datetime timestamp for the hits in the synchronisation sequence, the first peak of

Figure 2. Cross-correlational alignment of audio-derived sync cue template and the jerk magnitude from a Movesense accelerometer recording with the embedded motion. **Top:** The initial poor alignment between recording time and device timestamps. **Middle:** the cross-correlation between these time series excerpts to find best offset. **Bottom:** The aligned template and sensor signal in device timestamps for future timestamp correction.

the first cue sets Recording Time Zero, with all following event onsets measured in reference to it.

The peaks from the audio are then rendered at the same sample rate as the accelerometer recordings. The point-process is smoothed to resemble the shape of jerk magnitude from the accelerometers given the motion performed. Jerk magnitude is the most useful features of the accelerometer measurements because it peaks with the halt of motion which corresponds to the recorded sound of impact. The top plot of Figure 2 shows an example of the cue model from the peaks of Figure 1, expanded to fit shape of the shaker table hits (slower energy dissipation than small taps) against the instantaneous jerk magnitude from one of the smacked Movesense sensors in near alignment (light orange). Below that is the cross-correlation of these two excerpts, audio cue model and accelerometry feature, with a very obvious peak of maximum alignment. The last plot of Figure 2 shows the Movesense time series shifted to align with the audio device time.

The uneven (non-isochronous) hit sequence in the sync cue ensures that there is very little confusion in the cross-correlation. So long as device clocks are not wildly off (less than 10 s variation between devices), algorithmically identifying cue positions and visually confirming detection with a plot like Figure 2 takes only seconds per device.

2.2 Large scale deployment

Embedding parallel sharp hits in a large fleet of sensors becomes impractical without dedicated equipment. And when experiments run for days across multiple locations and dozens of experimenters and participants, an actively recording audio device can be a hazard and quickly lost. For our large scale concert experiments, two technological aids were constructed to facilitate post-recording synchronisation: a shaker table and the SyncSpider.

Figure 3. Photos of the shaker table built to embed parallel shake cues in dozens of active sensor devices. On the left is a side view of the table with multiple layers of Equivital SEM units. On the right an additional layer of AX3 and Movesense units arrange on their own plate. The shaker platform is pulled sharply to the rail bumper multiple times to produce a matching sync cue in the audio and sensor accelerometers. Photo credits RITMO and Kayla Burnim.

2.2.1 Shaker table

The shaker table was constructed from an extruded aluminum frame with an acrylic platform and additional optional shelves made from high density rigid foam (see Figure 3.) The bottom had a small layer of transportation grade foam aiding in securing and protecting the devices from damage during shaking. The base frame can be used alone or with up to 3 additional shelves, each shelf also lined with high friction foam to hold sensor devices in place. A top frame with a soft foam underside can be secured to the bottom with threaded rods to provide additional rigidity and compression to accommodate sensors of differing sizes. Shaker platform was set on a short low friction glide with a bumper, allowing smooth motion and firm hits to make strong peaks in instantaneous jerk captured simultaneously by all devices in the stacks (within sample rates of 256 Hz or less).

2.2.2 SyncSpider

The SyncSpider was a Zoom H6 portable recorder mounted on a medium Joby GorillaPod stand and dressed in a handcrafted jumping spider costume⁶ (see Figure 4.) Besides recording the synchronisation taps before and after the activities of each day, the SyncSpider was a companion to the wearable sensors, accompanied participants into performances spaces, activity rooms, and temporary experiment stations. The construction made the device more noticeable as an active recording device in non-laboratory spaces turned to experimentation, and it was also more easily tracked by the team of researchers moving between multiple locations within in a large venue. "Where is the SyncSpider?" was a quick question to answer as we coordinated the capture of unique events according to external performance and workshop schedules. While it could not record the best sound from its resting position off to

⁶ Jumping spiders may seem like an odd costume for a microphone as they do not have ears or an auditory system comparable to that of vertebrates, however they have been demonstrated to be sensitive to certain frequencies of air-borne vibrations through their leg hairs [5].

Figure 4. The SyncSpider audio recorder from above and deployed in a rehearsal space (right) before the musicians enter. Photo credits Finn Upham and RITMO.

the side of the action, the SyncSpider’s audio files were sufficient to define when events occurred, supporting segmentation of aligned biosignal sensor measurements to the intervals of experimental interest. These recordings also facilitated alignment with other audio-visual recordings of specific events.

3. RESULTS

This process of embedding synchronous cues in accelerometer measurements has exposed the need for corrections to device clock timestamps. Besides differences in how each type of device varied in clock initialisation and drift errors (time gained or lost relative to external clocks), these corrections also show substantial variation between units of the sensor.

Table Table 1 shows the between-unit standard deviation cue time for each cue in one recording session involving all three sensor systems discussed so far. These datalogging devices differ substantially in the quantity of variance per cue. At the first cue, performed within an hour of initialisation, the AX3 device clocks differ measurably less than others, however unit differences were still substantial for our target precision. The Equivital sensors, which are set to record respiration chest stretch, electrocardiography, skin temperature as well as acceleration, started with almost a second of deviation.

After many hours of recording (roughly 7-11 hours here, depending on the sensor type), the dispersion across second cues is always larger than at the first. Table Table 1 shows how the Equivital sensor measurements spread had nearly doubled over the course of a dress rehearsal and long concert performance. The AX3 and Movesense units drift less, but a few hundred milliseconds is substantial enough to seriously confound measurements of inter-participant coordination and alignment with audio and visual recordings of the performances.

These trends per system are helpful but not enough to correct individual measurements because drift also varies between units. Figure 5 reports the hourly clock drift measured in the Equivital SEM unites between synchronisation cues in five days of recording per unit serial number. Besides a set from an earlier batch (starting with 3), these units lost on average 250 ms per hour of recording, how-

Sensor	Hz	Units	Cue 1	Cue 2
Equivital SEM	256	68	776 ms	1304 ms
Axivital AX3	250	12	10.5 ms	195 ms
Movesense	104	10	234 ms	356 ms

Table 1. Internal clock deviations between three types of datalogging sensors during one concert experiment recording day (Bodies in Concert, KORK 2024). After ACC sensor sample rates and number of unites recording, the two cue columns specify the standard deviation of cue timing between units in their original timestamps in milliseconds.

Figure 5. Distributions of clock drift calculated per Equivital SEM device overall measurement days with two synch cues. Some sensors were only used once or twice.

ever the clock drift is more consistent within units than between them, with some variation in drift within a few units in this data sets (SSO 2024). One plausible explanation for this inconsistency is unit battery levels, another might be signal processing demand but this last factor has not been evaluated directly. Regardless, evaluating drift per recording with two synchronisation cues continues to be a necessary practice.

In the previously implemented tapping protocol for embedding cues in devices already worn by participants, the gains of alignment to within 100 ms was a serious improvement from initial dispersions of 0.58 s from devices in the hall and 13 s across live-stream viewers. Still the shaker table protocol for synchronisation improves alignment to within sample rate and requires less time and effort to retrieve embedded cues in the accelerometer signals.

Figure 6 shows an example of how theses synchrony gains facilitate research on these wearable sensor measurements with music. Heart rate is often looked at on the scale of minutes, however aligned beat-wise measurements from musicians and audience show alignment in more fine-grained fluctuations. In figure 6, the normalised instantaneous heart rates of each member of an orchestra and several audience members during 3 hour music concert experiment are plotted together, including intermission. The conductor’s heart rate can be followed in a single row across the top, peaking at the end of the music coded as Saev1 but varying substantially throughout. Within sections, such as the brass and woodwinds, there is a startling coherence during music as players hearts’ slow and speed up with the lung pressures involved with playing parallel passages.

Figure 6. Aligned range-normalised heart rate time series per participant (55 musicians upper rows, 22 Audience members lower rows) during the 3 hour KORK 2025 Bodies in Concert experiment performance, with intervals of speech and music shaded according to timestamps from SyncSpider audio. Precise vertical striping textures within woodwinds and brass sections demonstrate the relevance of high precision alignment, even in supposedly slow signals like heart rate.

In figure 7, this alignment advantage helps understand the relationship this signals to musical actions at the scale of notes played. Combining measurements from single brass player during six concert performances of the same music, we see respiration and heart rate changing before, during, and after intervals played.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This accelerometer-based synchronisation procedure has allowed us to use combinations of commercial datalogging sensors where wired and live-streaming systems would be hard to manage: with dozens of sensors recording concurrently in real performance venues. This process adds only minutes to recording sessions, and, when successfully followed, results in signals aligned to within each device's accelerometer sample period with only seconds of effort per unit.

This procedure isn't fool proof: distributed wearable devices fail can fail to record or prematurely stop due to human error or any number of unexpected factors. Similarly human error can interfere with the audio recording in ways that challenge the extreme precision this process aims to supply. In one experiment, the SyncSpider was not set to record properly, and the costume prevented researchers from noticing the issue until it was too late to correct. Thankfully the previous measurements with high quality alignment between other audiovisual measurements and the physiological signals facilitated the identification of cues that could be used to connection measurements after the device signals were synchronised among themselves. In these orchestra concert recordings, the oboist inspiration timing during tuning, always a sequence of three long

sustained notes started in relative quiet, and with multiple tunings captured in that days recording sessions, these points were enough to reconnect the physiological and audio-video recordings to within 40 ms (musician respiration sample rate: 25.6 Hz).

The shaker table and SyncSpider used for experiments throughout 2024 were initial iterations of these forms. We expect to continue to improve upon this synchronization procedure by both expanding the devices as well as automation. These cross platform studies often include other human signal measurement technology such as eye tracking glasses and motion capture as well as various video devices. The shaker table was constructed as a proof of concept, meant to be low cost, low weight, and easy to use. Potential updates to the shaker table include a programmable motor for agitation for pre-sequenced cue forms and adjustments for portability. The SyncSpider's costume has gotten a little worn down, but the principle of a long-running audio recorder for anchoring physiological measurements to external clocks continues to be a useful strategy, even in measurement situations where a cat-sized spider would be awkward to bring along. Feature-based annotation of these audio recordings and the full alignment sequence could become substantially automate.

For now, however, the protocol for accelerometry-embedded synchronisation cues has proven sufficient for supporting the deployment of convenient wearable biosensors in a variety of real world musical activities, from KPop concerts to orchestra rehearsal, to dancing at an office Christmas party. The resultant aligned measurements offer a wealth of information about coordinated musical behaviours to be studied for years to come.

Figure 7. Equivital sensor measurements of quantity of body motion, respiratory rate, respiratory wave (phase), and heart rate (10 beat median) from one brass player during 6 performances of the same piece. Signals aligned with precision through audio dynamic timewarping, with shared trajectories much clearer due to the initial measurement-audio alignments per performance. Heart rate and respiratory rate (breath duration) include highlights (cyan) of when this musician is playing during this arrangement of Rossini’s William Tell Overture.

Acknowledgments

This project is supported by the Research Council of Norway through projects 262762 (RITMO), and 322364 (fourMs). Our thanks to the many colleagues and participants involved in the experiments reported on.

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